

Exploring Digital Divide in Education: A Multiple Case Study

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ABSTRACT

This is a qualitative research approach using the multiple case study design which aimed to explore the Digital Divide in Education of the Junior High School learners of Talisay National High School. The study focused on two cases, the learner's perception whose learning experiences are aided by access, and possession of digital devices, and the learner's perception whose learning experiences are not aided by access, and possession of digital devices. It was done through one-on-one in-depth interviews with each participant. The data was analyzed in two stages namely, the within-case analyses where the data of each participant was thoroughly analyzed and followed by the cross-case synthesis. Based on the result of the study, learners who are aided by digital devices describe their experiences as helpful, challenging, and having a positive and negative impact. Learners conclude that digital devices are useful and helpful in their studies like creating presentations, making reports, answering assignments, and other school-related activities. In the second case, learners who are not aided by access to digital devices describe their experiences as difficult, challenging, and having less opportunity to learn. It presents that learners are always behind on the activities, and they have less opportunity to learn new things. Additionally, learners have a low performance in their learning because of the absence of digital devices. Moreover, this study served as the basis for the formulation of an innovation on improving student's learning using digital devices.

Keywords: *learner's perception, learner's experiences, digital device*

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INTRODUCTION

There is a global discussion concerning the issue of the haves and have-nots (Ryan, 2018). Most research on the subject has covered what has come to be known as the "digital divide", or the separation between those who have access to, and can effectively use technology, and those who do not (Huffman, 2018). Although swift advances in technology have occurred and technology use in educational settings is helpful in increasing the access and quality of learning (Domingo & Garganté, 2016). Furthermore, despite significant progress in the worldwide use of the internet and related technologies, persistent inequalities continue to exist in terms of who has access to it and those who do not (Cruz-Jesus, F., Vicente, M. R., Bacao, F., & Oliveira, T., 2016). With this, Henry (2019) calls this inequity the "Digital Divide" which is defined as divisions "within and across societies according to those that have access to digital technologies (including the internet) and those that do not." Thus, Rogers (2016) refers to this issue as an important issue for social justice in the twenty-first century. The existence of the digital gap in different groups related to education such as among teachers and students should be considered as a matter of concern.

In the context of the teaching and learning process, Information Communication Technology (ICT) proves to be a significant domain and has become an object of interest to improve the effectiveness of education (Abidin & Jafre, 2018). Hence, Van Deursen, Heplspers, & Eynon, (2015) utilize digital skills in measuring the digital divide and found education to be the most important correlating factor wherein highly educated people perform better than others.

Studies investigating students' access to digital technologies, and explaining specific access types, have not been sufficiently reported in the existing literature. Further, the focus of existing work has been mostly limited to measuring physical access to digital devices. However, this issue is more nuanced, involving different facets - motivational, physical, skills, and usage access of ICT. With this, inequities may exist, and these inequities have far-reaching consequences when it comes to education since inadequate access to technology can hinder students from learning technology skills that are crucial to their success (Soltan, 2016).

Considering the above, the researcher believes that having a glimpse of the unique reality of the digital divide of herein locale may provide an equally unique perspective of the issue vital to the wider view of the world so that a more sustainable solution thereof may be afforded. Also, the researcher deems it of utmost interest to explore the digital divide in education that investigates the perceptions of learners whose learning experiences are aided or not aided by access, and possession of digital devices.

In the school where the study is conducted, new technology is used by some of the learners but not all learners have access to new technology and how to utilize the technology used. Based on the Learning Enrollment and Survey Form (LESF) conducted during the enrollment process, there are approximately 5% of learners enrolled at Talisay National High School have no devices available at home that the learners can use for their learning and almost 70% of the learners can connect to the internet through PISO Wi-Fi, they do not have own internet connection at home. This uneven access to new technology and utilization skills is known as the digital divide. This study has become important to find out the perceptions of

learners whose learning experiences are aided by access, and possession of digital devices and those who are not.

The purpose of this qualitative multiple-case study is to delve into learners' perceptions of the digital divide in the realm of education, with a particular emphasis on the experiences of those who are aided and those who are not aided by digital devices. This research aims to provide a rich and in-depth exploration of how students in diverse educational settings understand, interpret, and respond to digital disparities. Through an in-depth analysis of multiple cases, the researcher seeks to uncover the complexities and nuances of students' lived experiences as they navigate a digitalized educational landscape and to determine the effects of these views on the learning outcomes, involvement, and general well-being of students. The result of this study not only contributes to a deeper understanding of the digital divide but also informs educational policies and interventions that can bridge the gap and create a more equitable and inclusive educational experience for all students.

Research Questions

This study aims to explore the learner's experience in using digital devices for learning. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the perceptions of learners whose learning experiences are aided by access and possession of digital devices?
2. What are the perceptions of learners whose learning experiences are not aided by access and possession of digital devices?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Multiple case study research is a qualitative methodology that allows researchers to contrast between individual cases, represent a diversity of qualities and extremes to create depth, and understand a broad phenomenon without losing the individuality of the single case studies (Baxter & Jack, 2008; Thomas, 2011). In other words, multiple-case studies are considered more robust than single-case studies and the analytic findings that arise independently from multiple cases are more powerful than those coming from a single case (Yin, 2009).

This study employed a qualitative multiple case study because it focused on two cases. To thoroughly investigate a social phenomenon by comparing and contrasting differences between cases and considering each participant as an individual case, Yin (2017) suggested using a multiple case study. It helped the researcher to examine each case if there were similarities or differences through one-on-one in-depth interviews. Cross-case synthesis was utilized, this is a technique in data analysis in a multiple case study that helped the researcher to provide a detailed examination of the learners' perception through their experiences on the digital divide in education. Also, it helped and allowed to contrast between individual cases.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The participants of this study consist of two pairs of students. The first pair consist of two learners who have direct access to digital devices. The second pair composed of two learners who do not have direct access to digital devices.

Researcher selected the research participants through a presurvey to determine the appropriate learners who are aided and not aided in the access and possession of digital devices. To this end, only four learners were selected as participants of the study and who were invited for an interview. Then, a letter sent to the selected potential learners as participants requested as volunteers to take part in the interviews about their perception of the digital divide in education. Also, the researcher sent a parent consent letter to the selected participants on the study.

The participants of the study met the following selection criteria: for the first pair of participants, (1.) they are recently enrolled learners of Talisay National High School, (2.) they are learners whose learning experiences are aided by access, and possession of digital devices (3.) their status of the internet connection of the learners at home, (3.1 How do you connect to the internet? 3.1.1 own mobile data, 3.1.2 own broadband internet like DSL, wireless fiber, satellite, 3.1.3 other places outside the home with an internet connection like barangay/ municipal hall, neighbor, relatives, 3.1.4 Piso Wifi) (4.) their willingness to be interviewed and share their perception regarding the digital divide in education for the present study.

For the second pair of participants, (1.) they are recently enrolled learners of Talisay National High School, (2.) they are learners whose learning experiences are not aided by access, and possession of digital devices (3.) their willingness to be interviewed and share their perception regarding the digital divide in education. These criteria were used in the selection of the participants to ensure that the study's sample is relevant, representative, and aligned with the research objectives and research questions. These criteria helped the researcher to define the characteristics or attributes of individuals or entities who were part of the present study. In addition, the interview was conducted outside their class hours.

Research Instrument

In gathering the data, two sets of interview guide questions were formulated based on the research questions used as an instrument in this study. There were two sets of research guide questions since there were two pairs of participants used in the study. Each set of guide questions was composed of main questions and possible probing questions aimed to explore the digital divide in education for the Junior High School learners of Talisay National High School through a face-to-face series of interviews.

A coding sheet was used to extract the statements from the responses to the questions asked by the research participants. Their statements were listed in the coding sheet as well as the analysis and interpretation data to address what the research focus wants to reveal in this study. Also, a mobile phone was used to record the participant's statements during the interviews. The researcher also used her laptop to save the recorded interviews and save the files in a cloud to serve as a backup file. At the same time, she used notes during the interview to take down the important information regarding their experiences on the digital divide shared by the participants.

Data Gathering and Analysis

The method used in gathering the data was through interviews of the participants directly associated with exploring the digital divide in education by capturing the participants' experiences and points of view of the digital divide. The duration of the interview averaged 30 minutes per participant. With this, the following phase in the collection of data was observed. These include preliminary activity, main activity, and post-activity.

Preliminary Activity

In this stage of gathering the data, the researcher respectfully adhered to the established protocol for conducting the study on the perceptions of learners whose learning experiences are aided and not aided by access, and possession of digital devices at Talisay National High School. First, she requested permission from the Office of Graduate Studies at Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception. Upon receiving consent, she approached the school head of Talisay National High School to secure permission to conduct the study. Second, she sent a letter of consent to the parents or guardians of the participants, requesting permission for their child to be involved in the study. Third, she obtained the assent of the participants through the assent form which they signed, allowing them to participate in the study and data collection. In identifying the participants, the researcher conducted a pre-survey of the learners to determine whose learners are aided by access and possession of digital devices and whose learners are not aided by access and possession of digital devices. After the identification of the participants, she informed them of the nature of the study, when, where, and how the interview will be done. An interview schedule was designed with a stated interview guide featuring the most vital interview questions with suggestions for follow-up questions.

Main Activity

After identifying the research participants and obtaining all the necessary consent and assent letters, researcher explained to them the purpose of the study and the steps to be observed during the interview so that she could protect their confidentiality. At the beginning of the interview, she had a preliminary conversation with the participants so that they felt relaxed in sharing their insights or points of view about the digital divide in education. Then, she proceeded to the main questions found in the interview guide based on the research questions. During the interviews, the researcher took down notes and recorded the information shared by the participants through an audio-video form with the use of a mobile phone with the consent of the participants.

All the interviews conducted took place at the participants' s choice and all the participants chose to be interviewed at Talisay National High School being the research environment. The interviews used the English language and were interpreted into vernacular dialect to ensure that no language barrier hindered the gathering of rich data as the medium of instruction. Participants in this study were allowed to use the Bisaya dialect to express their experiences. The researcher was not concerned about the specific rules and the order in which questions were made during the interview to construct bonds and reliance with the participants through profound discussions of the participants' insights or points of view about the digital divide in education as they recounted and described their stories about the way they access, utilize the digital devices in their respective learning areas.

Post Activity

In the last stage, right after all the interviews were conducted, researcher directly saved and stored all the gathered data on the laptop which also contained a password code for security purposes. The recorded data was also saved on the cloud application for backup purposes. Additionally, to preserve the participants' anonymity, they were referred to by labels learners' access for the first pair and the second pair learners' no access. She asked them to complete and sign the post-interview confidentiality form for additional feedback on how they would prefer to have their data managed.

After the transcription of the data gathered, she asked them if the selected data they shared would be fine for them to be included in the result of the study. Lastly, she gave a simple token of appreciation to the participants as a sign of gratitude for the valuable time they spent during the conduct of the interview.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Within-Case Analyses

Learner 1

In the interview conducted, the participant described his experiences in using digital devices for learning as helpful, challenging, and having a positive and negative impact.

Helpful. Digital devices are very helpful for young people, as it provides them with an alternative space where they can develop themselves and deal with different life challenges (Mascheroni and Ólafsson, 2014). Moreover, digital technology helps learners apply information and communication technology for various purposes (Smahel et al., 2020). Also, Rich et al., (2020) many learners find it helpful to use digital devices, such as smartphones, watches, and apps, to monitor their health (physical activity, menstruation), and to support some of its aspects.

In the present study, the participant emphasized that using digital devices in learning helps a lot, especially in making projects, assignments, and other related school activities. In addition, he highlighted that having direct access to digital devices makes his work easy and gives more additional information on his lessons such as doing an experiment and making PowerPoint presentations or reports. As the participant said that they have a lack of references, by using his device like surfing on the internet or YouTube and watching some video tutorials he can perform the task given to him. Also, learner 1 shared that having access to digital devices is a big help for him as one of the SSLG officers in making documents such making ACR, notification letters, and other required documents to be submitted to their SSLG adviser. Through different applications installed in the digital devices, did the required documents well like Google Docs. He easily disseminated information or announcements with the use of his digital device. Moreover, in terms of communication, the participant was grateful for having access to digital devices because he easily communicated and received messages instantly from her classmates and teachers. If he has queries and clarification on the school task, he can quickly ask through messenger. The participant shared the following statement:

“Ang digital devices tabang kayo namo maam especially sa among educational purposes like projects, assignments, presentation, tabang kayo siya maam”.

(The digital devices are very helpful to me, especially for our projects, assignments, and presentations, it is helpful)

Challenging. Despite having direct access to digital devices and being helpful for his learning. Learner 1 encountered challenges in using digital devices such as poor internet connection, lagging of digital devices, and lack of knowledge of using the digital device in learning that affects his performance. This finding supports the study of Chung et al.,(2020b) which reveals that one of the major challenges of online learning for students is access to the internet. The students struggle in attending online classes because of having poor and loss of internet connection. In addition, Yu et al. (2017) state that students’ lack of digital skills involves the lack of technical knowledge of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools, lack of access to computers and the Internet, the digital divide, and digital exclusion. It indicates that learners encountered challenges due to having a deficient capability of handling different technologies.

Experiencing these challenges, learner 1 submitted his output late, and sometimes he could not submit it. There are instances when he feels frustrated.

Positive and Negative Impact. The digital world offers them many opportunities for their personal development, but on the other hand, it can also bring many negative experiences that they have to deal with (Smahel et al., 2020). However, digital technology can also be a very useful tool in the lives of people if it is used appropriately. Their digital literacy, or ability to use digital technology for competent, autonomous, and safe communication, plays a crucial role in this process (Mascheroni and Ólafsson, 2014).

Learner 1 highlights that having direct access to digital devices has positive and negative impacts. He expressed that it has a good impact because it is helpful not just only in his learning but also in his life. It is good in such a way that all his tasks and activities in school are done easily and conveniently. Also, it helps to develop his critical thinking skills through exploring the different applications offered. However, he also cites that digital devices bring a negative impact such as overuse of digital devices. As learner 1 shared:

“Ang impact jud sa digital devices useful kaayo siya, helpul kaayo. Makatabang jud siya sa educational na purpose. Dili lang sa educational purpose kundi sa life pud. In terms sa communication, makatabang namo sa pagcommunicate sa ako family, friends especially sa ako parents na lagyo sila, makacommunicate ko within sa time na ako sila ma contact.

(The impact of digital devices is useful and helpful. It is helpful for educational purposes. It is not just for educational purposes but also in our lives. In terms of communication, it helps communicate with our families, and friends, especially my parent who are working abroad, I can communicate o the time they are available to reach.)

Learner 2

Throughout the interview, learner 2 described her experiences of having direct access to digital devices as helpful, challenging, and having a positive impact.

Helpful. The participant accentuated that having access to digital devices for learning is helpful in accomplishing school tasks like making reports, and assignments. She did her tasks easily and efficiently. This finding supports the study of Lupton (2021) explains that today's adolescents prefer to use online resources for information, mostly because of their easy and fast accessibility. With the use of digital devices, she can easily ask her teacher how to perform the given activities. She has an opportunity to explore how to manipulate some applications in digital devices that are useful for her learning such as making videos through the CapCut application. The participant describes her experiences in using digital devices for learning:

“Nakatabang siya maam sa akong pageskwela kinahanglan man magresearch. Madali nako ang akong himuonon na report kay magsearch ko sa google then, og nay mga assignments.”

(It is useful in my study; I need to have research on it. It is easy for me to accomplish the task making report because I used Google to find the information and also my assignments.)

Challenging. As to the challenges encountered by the participant such as managing the time in using the digital device and lack of skills in manipulating the digital device. This challenge affects her learning and performance in such a way that she submitted her output late and also, she had limited time to do the task. Sometimes, the participant experienced difficulty during their class activity since she had no laptop at home, only a mobile phone was the available digital device she had. In the study of Jin and Sabio (2018), mobile devices have the potential to be used and adapted for learning purposes. This lack of devices could affect students' studies; in which they can be left behind in the remoteness of learning.

That's why during their practical, the participant was uncomfortable in manipulating the devices, however, with the assistance of her teacher she made the practical. Moreover, the participant experienced difficulty in finding the exact information on the internet. The participant shared her challenges in using digital devices:

“Ang challenges na ako na encounter usahay unahon nako ang magcellphone kaysa maghimo sa assignments og project. Mao masayo nalang ko og mata para mahoman nako. Nay uban malate ko og submit kay mas unahon man nako ang pag cellphone ra.”

(The challenges I encountered is I do first my personal activity that doing my assignments and project. That is why I need to wake up early just to finish my task. Some output I submitted late because I had more time to focus on the non-educational activities.)

Positive Impact. Participant concludes that having access to digital devices is important for learning or has a positive impact. It lessens the burden of the learners in doing the task because by just using the digital device and accessing the internet, they find the information they want and it adds information for clarification of the particular lesson. She is more motivated to do the task because of the digital device she uses in her learning. Goodyear et al.,

(2021) state students can take more initiative and feel more like they are in the driver's seat when they use desktops and other gadgets in tandem with digital tools. In addition, Using technology for learning increases motivation and retention (Zheng et al., 2022).

Cross-Case Synthesis

Based on the within-case analyses of the data gathered and shared by the participants during their interview, both the participants who have direct access to digital devices conclude that having direct access to digital devices for learning is helpful and useful. Singh & Bathla, (2023) students are more engaged and have a better time learning when technological advances are used successfully in the classroom. They emphasize that having access to digital devices is a big help in accomplishing their school task and contributes a good impact on their learning. It highlights that digital devices provide learners with the most up-to-date information available by accessing their digital devices. It has a great impact on their learning in such a way learners feel convenient in doing their tasks. In addition, learners are grateful that they have direct access to the digital devices. By having access to digital devices, learners enjoy the way they do their tasks because it provides enough information to make their tasks easy and effective. With this, Lepp et al., (2015) state that there have been tremendous benefits of digital devices. Such as; the increased various ways to teach students in classes by making lessons more fun and enjoyable. Smart devices provide easy ways to access online learning anywhere, at any time, and at a cheaper cost (Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018).

Furthermore, it proves that digital devices make learning convenient for every learner. Also, having direct access to digital devices is very necessary in the studies of learners and it brings a positive impact on the learners to do the task given to them. They perform independently. That is why, if possible, learners must have their own digital devices or direct access to digital devices to have an opportunity to create a great experience in using the new technologies in their learning and they can find more ways to study their lessons. This finding suggests that having direct access to digital devices is very necessary in the studies of students. Thus, Sivalingam and Subbaiyan (2018) conclude that having direct access to digital technology and its applications gives people the possibility to gain knowledge or skills outside of formal education, allowing them to become independent learners who can choose what they want to study and how they want to study.

Within-Case Analyses

Learner 1

Based on the interview, the participant described his experiences of not having direct access to digital devices for learning as difficult, challenging, and having less opportunity in learning.

Difficult. Difficult refers to the challenges or obstacles that make tasks or processes harder to complete due to the lack of digital devices. The participant claimed that having no access to digital devices is difficult because he has no gadgets to be used in doing the tasks, he cannot perform well, he cannot study in advance, and he cannot add more information on the lessons taught by the teachers, and he always left behind on some updates related to school activities. The findings support the study of McLeod and Carabott (2016) which reveals that

students are struggling to achieve the basic level required in information and communications technology because of a lack of digital skills such as having no skills in using digital tools, digital technologies, and being not aware of how these technologies can be used for learning. The participant enumerates his experiences in learning without the use of technology.

“Sa ako na sitwasyon, ilabi na karon na halos tanan ipaagi na sa internet. Lisod para nako ang pagtuon sa uban na lessons kay kuwang ug mga gamit, kasagaran ang mga learning resources e-send sa mga group chat.”

(In my situation, especially today almost all used internet. It is difficult for me to study some of the lessons because lack devices, most of the learning resources were sent to the group chat.)

Challenging. Challenging are those problems and difficulties encountered in learning in the absence of digital devices. The participant emphasized that having no digital devices in learning makes his learning challenging which also affects her performance in school. He faced some challenges such as he cannot do the task given by his teacher. He cannot join the class or lessons on time. Also, he cannot communicate with her teachers if he has something to clarify regarding the output to comply. Sometimes, if there are announcements like meeting with the parents through messenger, the participant is not aware of the announcement since he has no direct access to the digital device. The results were congruent with the study of Sestak et al. (2020) which states that students need a device that allows them to complete increasingly complex assignments such as typing papers. The lack of devices would affect a student’s academic performance. Learner 1 who is not aided by digital devices shared his challenges:

“Ang challenges na ako na experience o nasinati kani way cellphone na magamit sa eskwela kay kanunay ko maawahi. Ahmm. kana Dili pod ko kahimo ug mga projects maam. Unya kana kuan pod Dili sad ko ka contact o makapangutana sa ako mga classmates, nila sir og maam kung naa ko ipangutana. Sa ako giingon maam, dili sad ko ka kamao mohimo og mga projects like kana projects na e download niya e print.”

(The challenges that I experienced is I do not have cellphone that can be use in my study, I always behind. I cannot do some of the projects. I cannot communicate on my classmates, teachers if I have to ask for clarification. As what I said I did not know how to make projects that need to download on the internet and to produce a hardcopy.)

Less Opportunity in Learning. The participant concludes he has less opportunity to learn because of having no direct digital devices used for learning. He is not exposed to the use of new technology. The knowledge learned is limited. He cannot explore more information. Also, he has less skill in manipulating some applications on the digital device that can used for his learning because of the absence of digital devices. This lack of devices could affect students’ studies; in which they can be left behind in the remoteness of learning. The more device types a student owns, the higher his or her level of learning readiness (Estira, 2020). The participant strongly suggests that it is necessary to have a digital device in learning so that the learning will not be compromised.

“Less jud ako nahibaw-an maam basta digital devices ag gamiton sa paghimo og activity. Kay Dili man ko expose anang cellphone, pero naa man sad koy nahibaw-an maam sa mga lessons og nakakuha sad ko og pasar na grades.”

(I have limited knowledge in terms of using the digital devices. I am not expose of the digital devices like cellphone, but I have still understood some of the lessons discussed by the teachers and I got a passing grade.)

Learner 2

The participant shared her experiences of not having direct access to digital devices for learning through an interview. He expressed her experience by describing her experiences as difficult, challenging, and having less opportunity for learning.

Difficult. The participant said in the interview that it is very difficult without direct access to digital devices used for learning especially if the task or activity requires access to the internet. Sometimes, she feels envious of her classmates because they have devices that they can use for their learning. Also, she emphasizes that having a digital learning device is necessary, especially in today's era where most of the activities involve the use of technology. Furthermore, the participant shared that there were instances when she was behind on school activities, and she got bored doing tasks that involved the use of a digital device. The participant describes her experience without the use of digital devices.

“As a student, wala jud koy kaugalingon na cellphone o gadgets na magamit sa akong pag-eskwela. Naay cellphone si mama pero dili to ka connect og wifi, keypad na cellphone ra.”

(As a student, I do not have own mobile phone or gadgets that can be used in my learning. My mother has a mobile phone but it cannot connect to wifi.)

Challenging. The participant shared that the challenges she experienced make her learning difficult such as making school activities that require the use of a cellphone. There are instances she left behind on the activities to comply. Another, she has a hard time communicating with her teachers for clarification on the required activities to do. She shared her experiences regarding not having access to digital devices for learning:

“Ang challenges na ako na encounter kanang maglisod ko og himo sa mga activities na magneed og internet or cellphone para magresearch.”

(The challenge I encountered is I experienced difficulty in making activities that need to use the internet or cell phone in searching.)

Less Opportunity in Learning. It emphasizes in the interview of the participant that she has less knowledge or opportunity to learn and explore more because of the absence of digital devices in her study. Also, she concludes that digital devices are important in learning.

“Wala man ko gadget na magamit sa akong pag-eskwela, so, limited jud ako opportunity na makakuha ko og mga additional na information, kanunay ko maawahi og dili ko kaayo makamao unsaon pagperform like maghimo og video presentation og uban pa na activity na mogamit og cellphone.”

(I have no gadget to use in my study, so I had less opportunity to explore additional information.)

Cross-Case Synthesis

The participants in the second case of this study conclude that having no access to digital devices for learning is laborious or difficult. They both find difficulty in learning if it engages on digital devices since they do not have digital devices that can be used for their learning. As a result, they are not up to date in some activities. They have less opportunity to deal with those activities that result in low performance or output.

In the within-case analysis of each participant, it is clearly shown that the lack of devices affects the learner's academic performance. Both participants conclude that learners who do not have access to gadgets in their online activities perform poorly in terms of learning performance. They have less opportunity to explore and expand their knowledge. They cannot discover their capacity to deal with digital devices since they are not exposed to them. They have less interest because they cannot relate to the task since they do not have resources to use and explore. Also, they are not motivated to learn more and to explore more their lessons, especially in dealing the digital devices. One participant is envious of her fortunate classmates who have complete learning devices used in making their school activities. One participant concluded that it is necessary to have a digital device for learning so that they can comply with the requirements and achieve better performance in academic. To make the learners more advanced, specifically, in finding and organizing the information gathered from the internet. Based on the participant's experiences of not having access to digital devices, they cannot easily adapt to the new ways of learning.

However, one of the participants found a way to deal with the identified problem in accessing digital devices to look for assistance. Learning online is new and can be hard to get the hang of, that is why reach out to your teacher or professor if you want to have extra help, more feedback and instruction (Students Training & Education in Public Service, 2022). Also, Anu (2022) stated that to manage time during online learning students need to seek help from their parents, friends and families so that they will not miss out on learning and at the same time work will be done. It is also shown in the findings on the within-case analyses that despite the challenges faced by the participant who is not aided by digital devices, she finds another way like asking for help from a person whom she knows can help her. She tried to catch up with the required activity by doing such a way as finding an alternative way through other people who are more expert and fortunate than them. In doing that, they have less learned skills in using digital devices for learning because they are not the only ones who perform the task given to them.

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

Based on the findings, the participants in this case have similar experiences in using the digital devices for learning. Both shared that digital devices are useful and helpful in their studies. With digital devices, they answered and made their output on time. There learning is more active, and they have a better performance. In terms of communication, both easily

communicate to their classmates and teachers if they have queries regarding the task given by the teachers.

Even though, they have a great experience in dealing with the digital devices in learning, the participants encounter problems or challenges.

The first participant experienced of poor internet connection and lagging of using the digital devices. The second participant had a problem of managing the time in spending the digital devices and lack of digital skills. But the second participant address these problems by asking her friends and teachers to assist her in utilizing the digital devices in making the task and the end she performs and submit her output on time. The participants prove that learning with digital devices provides more opportunity to explore more and learn more based on the experienced they shared during the interview.

Generally, both the participants in this second case conclude that learning without the support or used of digital devices is difficult. They both experienced difficulties such as, delay in the submission of output, behind on the announcement and activities sent on the respective group chat, cannot perform the task like making video presentation, and have limited knowledge in dealing with the digital devices for learning.

Also, they shared that they have limited opportunity to learn more about the lessons since they do not have gadgets to use for educational activities. However, the second participant find ways to cope that difficulty she faced by asking assistance or help to her.

Recommendations

From the analysis of data of the study, the following recommendations are:

1. Communicate to the school administrators about the concern to determine the exact intervention to be used to address the issues of digital divide in learning.
2. Foster partnerships between educational institutions, community organizations or the LGU and the technology providers to address the digital divide comprehensively.
3. Strengthen the parent-teacher collaboration to improve the learning styles of the learners especially in dealing with digital devices.
4. Conduct further studies on learner's more personal experiences that may have affected the described experiences based on the result of this study.

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